

Lithium extraction from mining and mineral processing wastes

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ABSTRACT

Due to increased demand on energy storage sector and limited worldwide reserves of lithium, sustainable and reliable sources of this critical metal are being sought. Mining and mineral-processing wastes remain one of world's largest waste streams and proper management of these wastes provides multiple benefits – saving natural resources, reducing supply risk and enhancing environmental performance. Therefore, in terms of their possible use as a cheap and available source of Li (and other valuable elements), the review paper evaluates various mining, industrial and mineral-processing wastes – waste aluminosilicates (including B clays), bauxite processing residues (including red mud or overhaul slag), coal gangue and coal ash, Sn-W clay residues and other wastes (e. g., rare earth molten salt electrolysis slag). The paper discusses physical, chemical and biotechnological methods used for Li extraction from these materials and documents that efficient extraction is technically feasible. To enhance the economic viability, co-extraction of Li and other critical elements (REE, Al, Rb, Cs, Ge, Ga, V, etc.) is evaluated as well. In addition to technologic and economic implications, overall framing of Li extraction from secondary sources in the context of environmental and social sustainability is discussed as well.

1. Introduction

As traditional combustion of fossil fuels is in many aspects environmentally unsustainable and unfriendly (global warming, greenhouse gas production, local weather variation, toxic emissions, etc.) (Ahmad et al., 2022; Kazmi et al., 2023; Růžicková et al., 2018; Wierońska-Wiśniewska et al., 2022), cleaner energy production technologies are being developed and used. Since energy production should be not only ecologic but also economic, the application of the necessary multi-objective optimization on the electricity market leads to increased demand on energy storage sector (energy needs to be harvested when available and stored until needed) (Koochi-Fayegh and Rosen, 2020; Nassar et al., 2015; Růžicková et al., 2019a, 2019b). Thus, due to worldwide shift to coal substituents (Raclavská et al., 2021, 2023; Tun et al., 2020) and decarbonization (Atabani et al., 2023; Coppola and Scala, 2021; Scala, 2016), global Li demand in 2021 and 2023 was 101 and 165 kt Li (International Energy Agency, 2024) representing a 63 % increase during these 2 years. And tremendous increase in Li consumption is also projected for foreseeable future – Li demand in 2050 is estimated to be about twice as high as in 2030 (International Energy Agency, 2024). Therefore it is not surprising that by far the most significant end-usage of

Li in 2023 were batteries (87 % of Li consumption) with minor proportions related to ceramics and glass (4 %), lubricant greases (2 %), air treatment (1 %) and medical applications (1 %) (US Geological Survey, 2024); an increase in battery demand is expected to continue also in the future (International Energy Agency, 2021, 2023). As global Li reserves are limited, it is not sustainable to rely indefinitely on higher exploitation and mining (thereby threatening the resources of future generations). Instead, the focus should be paid on developing innovation and recycling technologies to ensure sustainable, secure and reliable supplies of this critical metal (Bielowicz, 2021; International Energy Agency, 2024; Mousa et al., 2022).

Another urgent global concern is huge amount of wastes generated annually; it is generally accepted that recycling should be preferred to landfilling, stockpiling or other similar practices (Jedrusiak et al., 2023; Kucbel et al., 2019; Raclavská et al., 2018). Despite a long-term effort focused to reducing their amount, mining and mineral-processing wastes remain one of the world's largest waste streams (Bian et al., 2012; Tiruta-Barna et al., 2007), around 2 trillion tonnes of tailings and waste rock is projected to be totally generated by mining by 2050 (Hudson-Edwards et al., 2024; Vivoda et al., 2025a). Proper management of these wastes provides multiple benefits – saving natural resources, reducing supply risk, and enhancing environmental

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Nomenclature

LOI -	Loss on ignition
FA -	Fly Ash
EMH -	European Metals Holding
REE -	Rare Earth Elements
XRF -	X-ray Fluorescence
DMSO -	Dimethyl Sulfoxide

performance.

Therefore, the paper evaluates various mining, industrial and mineral-processing wastes in terms of their possible use as a source of Li (and other valuable elements). Section 2 summarizes Li levels and Section 3 deals with methods used for Li extraction from these materials. To enhance the economic viability, the possibility of co-extraction of Li and other critical elements is evaluated in Section 4. Based on the current knowledge gaps and limitations, suggestions for future research are proposed at the end of the paper.

2. Lithium concentrations in mining, industrial and processing wastes

Due to its high reactivity, in nature, Li does not exist in metallic form but in salts and minerals dissolved in brines or present in rocks (Barbosa et al., 2023). Li is the 25th most abundant element in the Earth's crust (Obut et al., 2022) – its levels in various rocks are in tens of ppm. Average Li concentration in Earth crust is 32 ppm (Yaroshevsky, 2006). Clarke value for Li in sedimentary rocks is 33 ppm (Ketrís and Yudovich, 2009) and average Li abundance in shale was estimated to be 60 ppm (Moyle P R and Causey J D, 2001). Li average levels in ultrabasic, basic, intermediate and acid rocks are around 0.5, 15, 20, and 40 ppm Li (Yaroshevsky, 2006).

There are numerous papers focused to elemental concentrations in various mining and mineral-processing wastes, but a suite of target elements does not always contain Li. Traditionally, the attention was preferably paid to more toxic and harmful elements due to environmental concerns or identification of polluting source; Li was often omitted also due to its low concentrations and low atomic number (Kantor et al., 2019; Li et al., 2016, 2016Védová et al., 2019). And if the rare and critical elements are evaluated in various wastes, the attention is focused primarily to REE elements (Bartoňová et al., 2018; Santos

et al., 2022; Wagner and Matiane, 2018).

Regarding the hard rock ores, Li is traditionally extracted from pegmatites (complex aluminosilicate deposits containing quartz, feldspar, spodumene or mica minerals) (Tadesse et al., 2019). Nevertheless, spodumene and micaceous tailings as well as other wastes originating from clay manufacturing still contain quite high Li levels, which is shown in Fig. 1. For rough estimate and evaluation, Li cut-off grades for pegmatites/clays are shown in the last 5 columns. Even if these values can be used only for rough evaluation, it indicates that there are certain tailings and wastes with comparable concentrations (1 micaceous tailing, 1 lepidolite processing waste and 1 lithium porcelain stone even clearly exceed these values) (Kuang et al., 2015; Siame and Pascoe, 2011). Moreover, mining cut-off grades include the cost of mining while waste materials are generally easily available.

Li concentrations in bauxite processing residues (e.g., red mud or overhaul slag) are depicted in Fig. 2. Cut-off grade values related to independent recovery of Li are rather high (2323 or 3252 ppm Li) (Wang et al., 2013); however, in case of comprehensive utilization of these wastes where Li is extracted along with other valuable components, the cut-off grade values are much lower – 232 and 372 ppm Li (Wang et al., 2013). Then these values are comparable with bauxite mine tailings values (Tang et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2013, 2020; Zhang et al., 2021).

Extremely high value (1.96 % Li) in waste Al electrolyte relates to dried and powdered sample (Tang et al., 2023) – it considerably exceeds even the cut-off grade for independent extraction of Li. Very high Li concentrations were published also for overhaul slags (Dong et al., 2024a, 2024b) or electrolytic Al slag (Cui et al., 2024).

There has been an exponential growth in coal-related critical elements research, with Li being an obvious example (Spears, 2025). Even if renewable energy sources are becoming increasingly important in global energy mix, there are still certain other industrial sectors where coal remains an important feedstock (Kucbel et al., 2024). During coal mining and preparation, huge amount of discard coal products are generated; therefore, there is a need to consider coal discards as a vital source of energy or critical elements (H. Chen et al., 2022; Wagner, 2008). Fig. 3 summarizes Li concentrations in coals, coal gangues and coal ashes (including cut-off grades) showing increasing Li abundances in these 3 types of materials generally in the order: Li in coal < Li in coal gangue < Li in coal ash.

This is in line with modes of occurrence of Li in most coals – Li is associated predominantly with mineral matter – namely the clays (e.g., adsorbed on kaolinite, chlorite and illite or present in cookerite) (Dai et al., 2012; D. Han et al., 2024; Spears, 2017; Yuan et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2021; Zuo et al., 2022), organic association is much less

Explanations: (a) Economically relevant cut-off grade value, (l) Operationally relevant cut-off grade value.

Conversion note: 1 ppm = 10⁻⁴ %

Fig. 1. Li concentrations in waste aluminosilicates (^a Castor and Henry, 2020; ^b Ertan, 2023; ^c Ertan, 2020; ^d Iqbal, 2015; ^e Kuang et al., 2015; ^f Maulidia et al., 2023; ^g Moyle P R and Causey J D, 2001; ^h Obut et al., 2022; ⁱ Ozbas R and Derum E M, 2021; ^j Roy et al., 2022; ^k Siame and Pascoe, 2011; ^l Sterba et al., 2019; ^m Wærsted et al., 2023; ⁿ Wang et al., 2020; ^o Yusupov et al., 2015).

Explanations: (h) Economically relevant; * Overall cut-off grade; **Average Li grade for ore body. Conversion

note: 1 ppm = 10⁻⁴ %

Fig. 2. Li concentrations in bauxite and red mud residues (a Cui et al., 2024; b Dong et al., 2024a; c Dong et al., 2024b; d Gu et al., 2018; e Gu et al., 2020b; f Tang et al., 2022; g Tang et al., 2023; h Wang et al., 2013; i Wu et al., 2023; j Zhang et al., 2021).

Explanations: (m) Economic mining grade calculated as four times the average Li content in Chinese coal.

Conversion note: 1 ppm = 10⁻⁴ %

Fig. 3. Li concentrations in coal, gangue and ash (a H. Chen et al., 2022; b Dai et al., 2010; c Dai et al., 2023; d Gao et al., 2024; e Gong et al., 2016; f Hu et al., 2018; g C. Li et al., 2023; h J. Li et al., 2023; i Li et al., 2017; j Rezaei et al., 2023; k Saikia et al., 2015; l Sun et al., 2010; m Sun et al., 2012; n Xie et al., 2023; o Xing et al., 2024; p Xu et al., 2022; q Yang et al., 2014; r Yudovich and Ketris, 2015; s Zhang et al., 2022; t Zhou et al., 2022; u Zou et al., 2023).

represented (D. Han et al., 2024; Sun et al., 2013). Six-step chemical extraction of coal gangue led to the conclusion of 85.56 % Li in an aluminosilicate form with a small fraction in sulfidic form (Dai et al., 2023). This is in line with the Tessier’s sequential extraction procedure that revealed 90.74 % Li in residual (aluminosilicate) form with 6.83 % in Fe-Mn oxides (H. Chen et al., 2022) and quite low Pearson’s correlation coefficients between Li and macerals calculated for No. 6 coal seam Soutpansberg Coalfield in South Africa (Li-Vit = 0.36, Li-Int = 0.36, Li-Lip = 0.41; while Li-Al = 0.68) (Biswas et al., 2024). Predominant aluminosilicate Li association revealed also in case of intruded coals collected from both sides of a dolerite dyke (No. 2 Seam of the Witbank Coalfield, South Africa) (Moroeng et al., 2024). In coal fly ash, Li is mainly associated with non-magnetic fraction - aluminosilicates or glass fraction (Cao et al., 2024).

Therefore, in general, the lowest Li concentrations in coals can be attributed to the highest content of organic matter (that is generally depleted in Li). Coal gangue generally contain up to 25 % of organic

matter (Gao et al., 2021) and unburned carbon levels in coal ashes are in most power stations even lower (Bartoňová, 2015). There are also differences between minimum coal mining (and economic) grades of 80 (120) ppm Li proposed by (Sun et al., 2012) and Li cut-off grade for coal-bearing sequences related to ash basis (372 ppm Li) published by (Zou et al., 2023).

Fig. 3 indicates that Li concentrations in most coal ashes are comparable with Zou’s cut-off grade (the last column) related to coal ash basis (372 ppm Li) whereas Li levels in coal gangues are similar as cut-off grade value for coal by (Sun et al., 2012) – 80(120) ppm; nevertheless, their ash content is higher than that of coal.

Extremely high Li concentration (550 ppm Li) relates to Li-rich coal residue with high ash content (79.22 %) and low calorific value (Xie et al., 2023). Very high Li levels - 437.43 (Zhang et al., 2022) and 421.5 ppm Li (H. Chen et al., 2022) - were published for coal gangues from coal preparation plants in Inner Mongolia, China with 29.61 and 28.4 % LOI. In the latter study, Li concentrations was further increased when using

2.4–2.6 g/cm³ density fraction or >0.25 mm size fraction – in both cases the Li levels exceeded 500 ppm Li (H. Chen et al., 2022). Detailed study of Li in semi-anthracite Qinshui Basin (Gaoping mine) reported average Li content in no. 15 coal as 66.59 ppm, but extremely high Li levels were observed in the coal parting (566 ppm) and floor (396 ppm) (P. Han et al., 2024), which is in line with observation of Hou et al. (2022); Hou et al. (2022) concluding that the dominant source of Li in coal (gangue) is not organic matter but minerals (namely aluminosilicates).

In case of coal fly ash, the two finest particle-size fractions provided the highest Li concentrations (with enrichment factors 1.15–1.20) as well as the two lightest density fractions (with enrichment factors 1.20–1.26) (C. Li et al., 2023). As shown in Fig. 3, the highest Li concentration in coal FA (930 ppm Li) was published for PCC power plant Shuozhou, China (Li et al., 2017). This value is even 3-fold higher than 372 ppm Li cut-off grade (Zou et al., 2023).

Nevertheless, some caution is needed due to U and Th present in coal/ashes (Parzenty and Róg, 2019), average world coal levels of Th and U are 3.2 and 1.9 ppm Li (Parzenty and Róg, 2019; Yudovich and Ketris, 2015).

Fig. 4 summarizes the concentrations of Li in Sn-W clay residues and other tailings (Au or Mo-ore tailings). Upgraded mineral resource estimate by EMH (2021) for resources in the Cínovec deposit (Czech Republic) provided the cut-off grade of 0.1 % Li (0.22 % Li₂O) (European Metals Holding Limited, 2021). Fig. 4 shows that Au wastes or tailings exhibit quite low Li levels as well as Mo-ore or phosphate wastes (Kumkrong et al., 2022; Moyle P R and Causey J D, 2001; Tavakoli Mohammadi et al., 2015; Yurkevich et al., 2023). In contrast, most Sn-W/zinnwaldite wastes (Jandová et al., 2009; Kumar et al., 2023; H. Li et al., 2022; Samková, 2009) clearly exceed the cut-off grade value (European Metals Holding Limited, 2021). Absolutely the highest Li concentrations relate to the rare earth molten-salt electrolysis slag - 1.64, 1.79 and 2.29 % Li (Hu and Wang, 2021; X. Li et al., 2024; Tong et al., 2023), which is a waste material containing also high concentrations of other valuable elements (e.g. REE) (Yang et al., 2024).

Overall comparison of Li levels in secondary sources according to

their industrial origin (Figs. 1–4) documents that Li concentrations are in the range of several orders of magnitude. Despite the differences in individual samples, certain general trends can be inferred. The lowest Li levels are in the coal gangue and coal ash samples – generally within the range of 100–500 ppm Li (H. Chen et al., 2022; Dai et al., 2023, 2010; Yang et al., 2014); higher values - 900 ppm - are rather the exception (Li et al., 2017). Li levels in aluminosilicate-processing residues are around one order of magnitude higher (ca. 4000–5000 ppm) – e.g. in micae waste tailings (Siame and Pascoe, 2011), lepidolite-processing residues (Kuang et al., 2015) or in Li-porcelain stone (Wang et al., 2020); zinnwaldite-bearing wastes contain around 2000–3000 ppm Li (Jandová et al., 2009; H. Li et al., 2022; Samková, 2009). Extremely high Li concentrations were observed in waste sources originated from two industrial branches – from Al extraction from bauxite and from REE production. Electrolytic Al slag/overhaul slag can contain up to 14 000–16 000 ppm Li (1.6 % Li) (Cui et al., 2024; Dong et al., 2024b); waste aluminium electrolyte in dried form contained nearly 20 000 ppm Li (2 % Li) (Tang et al., 2023). A rich source of Li is also REMSES (rare earth molten-salt electrolysis slag) containing around 16 000–23 000 ppm Li (1.6–2.3 % Li) (Hu and Wang, 2021; X. Li et al., 2024). Such Li levels (ca. 1–2 % Li) are comparable with Li concentrations in certain traditional Li ores, such as lepidolite (with common Li levels 1.5–2.5 % Li) (Mertineit and Schramm, 2019; Tian-ming et al.; Timich et al., 2023) documenting that Li extraction from mining and minerals processing wastes is undoubtedly worth further research.

Nevertheless, Li recovery potential depends not only on the Li concentration but also on its mineral association and how easily it can be mobilized. For example, waste brines are advantageous as they contain Li in dissolved form (there is no need to roast them and/or leach Li by aggressive chemicals) – which is environmentally and economically beneficial. Even though tailings generally require roasting and/or leaching, their advantage is their fine-grained structure; therefore, the expenses for grinding, milling and similar practices are much lower than in case of coarse-grained slags or gangues. And general advantage of all these secondary sources (in comparison of traditional Li ores) is that

Explanations: (a) Evaluated in accordance with the guidelines of the JORC Code (2012); *REMSES – rare

earth molten-salt electrolysis slag. Conversion note: 1 ppm = 10⁻⁴ %

Fig. 4. Li concentrations in Sn-W clay residues and other mining wastes (^a European Metals Holding Limited, 2021; ^b Franzaring et al., 2018; ^c Hu and Wang, 2021; ^d Huang et al., 2020; ^e Jandová et al., 2009; ^f Kumar et al., 2023; ^g Kumkrong et al., 2022; ^h Li et al., 2022; ⁱ X. Li et al., 2024; ^j Mamani et al., 2020; ^k Martin et al., 2017; ^l Moyle P R and Causey J D, 2001; ^m Samková, 2009; ⁿ Shuiping et al., 2024; ^o Shumilova et al., 2022; ^p Tavakoli Mohammadi et al., 2015; ^q Tong et al., 2023; ^r Yurkevich et al., 2023).

they are easily available without mining.

3. Methods

Numerous physical and chemical methods are used for Li recovery from mining and mineral-processing wastes; generally, physical separation methods are used for the preparation of the concentrate where Li levels can be further enriched (or directly extracted out of it) by other methods, such as roasting and/or leaching (Fig. 5). It was shown that optimized milling/disintegration of the sample prior to application of physical or chemical methods can significantly enhance the extraction efficiency (Urakaev et al., 2020). Due to great variability of matrixes in mining and mineral processing wastes, detailed description of individual extraction schemes is discussed separately according to origin of waste source in sections: 3.1. Aluminosilicates, 3.2. Bauxite processing residues, 3.3. Coal and coal gangue and 3.4. Zinnwaldite and other mining wastes.

3.1. Waste aluminosilicates

Wastes from aluminosilicates processing can still contain quite high Li levels leading to testing of various procedures of Li extraction from these materials.

Kaolin mining waste (Fig. 6A) was first pre-concentrated by flotation and high-intensity wet magnetic separation to increase the original Li_2O concentration (0.84 % Li_2O) to 2.07 %. This pre-concentrate was then roasted with CaSO_4 or Na_2SO_4 leading to 84–97 % Li extraction (Siame and Pascoe, 2011). Comparison of Li extraction efficiency from spodumene after roasting at 1000 °C with Na_2SO_4 , $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ revealed the best extraction efficiency in case of Na_2SO_4 (93.8 % Li was converted into LiNaSO_4) (Qiu et al., 2023). Another successful procedure was applied to lepidolite processing gypsum residue (Fig. 6A) containing 0.95 % Li_2O – after NaOH solution digestion (0.5–10 MPa) and filtration, Li_3PO_4 was precipitated with 87.98 % yield (Kuang et al., 2015). In case of bauxitic claystone (Gu et al., 2020a), it was concluded that calcination could effectively increase the extraction efficiency; nevertheless, the calcination temperature should not be too high (calcination temperature exceeding 600 °C led to decreasing Li leachability).

Boron clays wastes (Fig. 6B) are another promising source of Li. Common approach is based on roasting with various salts at 750–1000 °C followed by water leaching. The highest Li extraction (90.41 %) was obtained by $\text{CaCl}_2 + \text{NaCl}$ roasting; high efficiencies was shown also for $\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{CaCO}_3$ (88.16 %) and H_2SO_4 (85.7 %) roasting (Büyükburç et al., 2006; Ertan, 2020; Obut et al., 2022). Roasting of B clays at 750–1000 °C is usually conducted only for 1 h but it still requires energy to heat the sample. In contrast, using bioleaching

with *Aspergillus niger* for ca. 31 days does not require heating to high temperatures but it needs longer time period; Li extraction efficiency is then 78.67 % (Ertan, 2023) (Fig. 6B).

In addition to traditional (physico)chemical extraction procedures, the promising potential of phytoremediation and phytostabilization of Li (and V and Cr) was documented by Elektorowicz and Keropian (2015).

3.2. Bauxite processing residues

Neutralization of red mud (224 ppm Li) by 0.01M HCl or 0.5M oxalic acid followed by 25 % acetic acid leaching (Fig. 7) led to 58–60 % or 42–47 % Li leaching efficiency (Gu et al., 2020b). Higher leaching rates were achieved by means of mixed acid ($\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 + \text{H}_3\text{PO}_4$) at 100 °C from bauxite mine tailings (0.2 and 0.21 % Li_2O) – 96.6 and 96.35 % Li was leached (Wu et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2021). Roasting with 98 % H_2SO_4 at 300–375 °C in N_2 was used for dried aluminium cryolite electrolyte containing 1.96 % Li – Li recovery was 98.78 % (Dong et al., 2024a, 2024b, 2024c; Tang et al., 2023). In case of overhaul slags from Al industry, roasting with H_2SO_4 or CaSO_4 at 360–750 °C followed by water leaching provided >95 % Li extraction efficiencies (Dong et al., 2024a, 2024b, 2024c).

It can be hypothesized that (similarly as in case of coal and coal gangue (H. Chen et al., 2022; Qin et al., 2022)), roasting the sample supports the leaching efficiency; nevertheless, more research is needed to confirm/disprove this hypothesis due to rather different character of the original wastes. Nevertheless, quite low roasting temperature (300–750 °C (Dong et al., 2024a, 2024b, 2024c; Tang et al., 2023)) is similar as 600 °C used for coal (Zhang et al., 2020). Moreover, in addition to higher leaching efficiency and lower emissions, lower temperature of roasting is cheaper (than using temperatures exceeding e.g. 1000 °C).

3.3. Coal and coal gangue

Coal gangue contains various proportions of organic fraction and mineral matter with quite low Li levels; therefore, pre-concentration of Li by high-gradient magnetic separation helps to avoid consuming a lot of chemicals or energy for heating the whole material (Sun et al., 2024). Another practical pre-concentration techniques enabling removal of fractions depleted in Li are XRF sorting equipment in combination with vibrating feeder and electromagnetic impactor (Dai et al., 2023) or gravity separation (Yang et al., 2022). Methods of physical pre-concentration (particle-size separation, magnetic separation, density separation etc.) that can be used for FA samples prior to their leaching are discussed in detail in (Zhou et al., 2022).

It was shown (H. Chen et al., 2022; Qin et al., 2022) that direct leaching of coal gangue (by 3M HCl or by $\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}/(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$) was rather

Fig. 5. Pre-concentration and extraction methods for mining and mineral processing wastes.

Fig. 6A. Procedures of Li extraction from waste aluminosilicates (^a Gu et al., 2020a; ^b Kuang et al., 2015; ^c Siame and Pascoe, 2011; ^d Wang et al., 2020).

Fig. 6B. Procedures of Li extraction from B-clay wastes (^a Büyükburç et al., 2006; ^b Ertan, 2023; ^c Ertan, 2020; ^d Obut et al., 2022).

inefficient (Qin et al., 2022) with only <6 % Li leached (Fig. 8A). In contrast, roasting the gangue prior to leaching significantly increased the Li extraction efficiency (H. Chen et al., 2022; Kang et al., 2024; Qin et al., 2022) - Li extraction efficiency from coal gangue (421.5 ppm Li) after calcination at 600 °C and 3M HCl leaching (90 °C) reached 92.74 % (H. Chen et al., 2022). Roasting of coal gangue (107 ppm Li) with (NH₄)₂SO₄+NH₄Cl at 400 °C followed by water leaching leached 80.83 % Li (Qin et al., 2022). It is interesting in this context that calcination/roasting temperature is not too high (400 and 600 °C) which is in line with the conclusion of Zhang et al. (2020); Zhang et al. (2020) that maximum Li extraction from coal was achieved after 600 °C calculation (further increase in calcination temperature decreased the Li extraction efficiency). After 1.2M HCl leaching, 70–80 % Li was extracted. Good Li extraction efficiency was observed also by (Zhang et al., 2023) after 400 °C roasting the coal gangue followed by leaching in 2M HCl (94 % Li extracted). 70 % H₂SO₄ roasting at only 180 °C and water leaching extracted 84.42 % Li (Xie et al., 2024) (Fig. 8A). Another activation method (that can be applied on coal gangue prior to its thermal treatment) is mechanical activation (long grinding) (Guo et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2024). For example, milling coal FA with sodium pyrosulfate efficiently improved the Li extraction rate (Fang et al., 2023).

In case of fly ash (FA), good results were achieved by sulphatising sintering (Fig. 8B) followed by acid leaching thereby extracting 95.6 % Li. Alkali leaching (followed by carbonation, evaporation and Li₂CO₃ precipitation) provided 85.3 % Li leaching rate (Qin et al., 2015). Another study (Li et al., 2017) documented that the efficiency of 6M HCl leaching can be enhanced by pre-desilication of FA by NaOH solution at

120 °C; then 82.23 % Li was leached (Li et al., 2017). Comparison of various thermal activation additives led to the conclusion that Na₂CO₃ provided better Li extraction efficiency than NaOH, NaCl, CaO, CaCO₃, (NH₄)₂SO₄, CH₃COONH₄ or NH₄Cl; and, that leaching performance of citric acid was better than that of tartaric or lactic acid (C. Li et al., 2024). Good extraction efficiency (>88 % Li) after Na₂CO₃ roasting at 800–850 °C was also achieved by (Gao et al., 2024; Rezaei et al., 2022, 2023). If 0.5M citric acid was used instead of 3M HCl, Li extraction efficiency decreased from 88–90 % to 70–80 %; nevertheless, 0.5M citric acid is less hazardous than 3M HCl (Gao et al., 2024). Organic acids are produced also during bioleaching – e.g. *Pseudomonas putida* produced 65.76 % gluconic acid, 11.66 % oxalic acid and 7.23 % citric acid (Rezaei et al., 2023). Bioleaching was successfully used to extract also other valuable elements from coal FA – hydrothermal treatment (NaOH, H₂SO₄, 150 °C, 0.476 MPa, 24 h) followed by *Aspergillus niger* bioleaching led to the extraction of 89.20 % Ti, 32.00 % Ga, 54.30 % Sr and 35.40 % Ba (but Li was not evaluated in this study) (Su et al., 2020).

3.4. Zinnwaldite and other mining wastes

Procedures used for Li extraction from Ta-Nb tailings or zinnwaldite-containing wastes are depicted in Fig. 9 indicating that physical separation methods (e.g. magnetic separation) are commonly used for the pre-concentration of Li in Ta-Nb mine tailings (Huang et al., 2020) or zinnwaldite wastes (European Metals Holding Limited, 2021; Martin et al., 2017). While in case of Ta-Nb mine tailings (0.61 % Li₂O) the non-magnetic residue (0.68 % Li₂O) was used for further processing

Fig. 7. Procedures of Li extraction from bauxite processing residues (^a Cui et al., 2024; ^b Dong et al., 2024a; ^c Dong et al., 2024b; ^d Dong et al., 2024c; ^e Gu et al., 2020a; ^f Tang et al., 2023; ^g Wu et al., 2023; ^h Zhang et al., 2021).

(Huang et al., 2020, p. 20), Li enrichment in zinnwaldite-bearing waste is achieved by magnetic retention of zinnwaldite grains (zinnwaldite is paramagnetic) (Jandová et al., 2010; Siame and Pascoe, 2011). Flotation is another promising approach for the preparation of Li-concentrate (Huang et al., 2020; Li et al., 2017). Current research (H. Li et al., 2022) documents that the flotation performance can be efficiently improved by previous microbial pre-treatment by silicate bacteria *LM-1*.

Typical efficient processing of zinnwaldite concentrate includes CaSO₄ + Ca(OH)₂ or CaCO₃ sintering (825–950 °C) followed by water leaching (Jandová et al., 2009, 2010; Vu et al., 2013). Numerous authors use calcareous additives (i.a.) due to the retention of F contained in zinnwaldite that is toxic and volatile and could be abundant in emissions; Ca-bearing additives bound F thereby forming CaF₂. For example, 91.32 % Li extraction recovery was achieved by using CaO + B₂O₃ with calcium - boron ratio of 3 based on both high extraction efficiency of Li (and Rb) and minimizing F emission originating from zinnwaldite at the same time. Sole B₂O₃ provides even moderately higher Li recovery (than CaO-B₂O₃ blend) but CaO is added to significantly reduce F emissions (forming CaF₂) (Shuiping et al., 2024).

Another promising waste material containing high Li levels is rare earth molten salt electrolysis slag (with ca. 1–2 % Li) (Hu and Wang, 2021; X. Li et al., 2024; Tong et al., 2023). Even if the extraction procedures vary greatly, extraction efficiency is in all cases very high (>99 % Li leached) (Hu and Wang, 2021; X. Li et al., 2024; Tong et al., 2023).

3.5. Extraction methods comparison

As shown in Fig. 6A and B, 7, 8A, 8B and 9, the most common extraction methods are acid and alkaline treatment, roasting with various salts and bioleaching, which is summarized in Table 1 along with major advantages and drawbacks of these procedures.

Acid treatment is common in case of bauxite-processing residues (red

mud, tailings etc.) where acetic acid and sulfuric acid (sometimes blended with phosphoric acid) provide good results. The temperatures are generally lower than in case of salt roasting which reduces energy costs. Acid method with H₂SO₄ is widely used and is highly adaptable to variability of the composition of starting material (Cao et al., 2024; Tian-ming et al.; M. Yang et al., 2025); nevertheless, low selectivity may place greater demands on subsequent separation (Sarker et al., 2022).

Alkaline treatment is less common in these materials; nevertheless, it was successfully used for Li extraction from lepidolite processing gypsum residue (Kuang et al., 2015) or for desilication of fly ash by NaOH (Li et al., 2017).

Waste materials originating from clay minerals processing are generally treated by *roasting with various salts*, such as CaCO₃, CaSO₄, or Na₂SO₄ that are often used in blends – Na₂SO₄+CaCl₂ (Wang et al., 2020) CaSO₄+CaCO₃ (Büyükburç et al., 2006) or CaCl₂+NaCl (Ertan, 2020). Roasting with salts is typically conducted at high temperatures 850–1050 °C, which can be somewhat costly. Na-salts are generally preferred to K ones as they are cheaper than their K counterparts. Roasting with calcareous salts (CaCO₃, CaO, CaCl₂ or CaSO₄) provides good results also in case of zinnwaldite-originated wastes (Jandová et al., 2010; Kristianová et al., 2023; Vu et al., 2013).

Bioleaching can be used either as a sole extraction method (Ertan, 2023) or in combination with salt sintering (Rezaei et al., 2023) which can further enhance the extraction efficiency.

It is worth mentioning that in case of REMSES (containing extremely high Li levels of 1–2 %), high extraction efficiencies can be achieved by various procedures – by salt roasting with CaO + Al₂(SO₄)₃ at 900 °C (Tong et al., 2023), by acid treatments (e.g. with HNO₃ at 250 °C (Hu and Wang, 2021)) and even by alkaline treatment (with CaO in hot water (X. Li et al., 2024)) – all these procedures provided >96 % extraction efficiency for Li.

Regardless of the preferred extraction method, using some *pre-*

Fig. 8A. Procedures of Li extraction from coal gangue and coal (^a H. Chen et al., 2022; ^b Qin et al., 2022; ^c Xie et al., 2023; ^d Xie et al., 2024; ^e Zhang et al., 2023; ^f Zhang et al., 2020). Conversion note: 1 ppm = 10–4 %.

concentration or activation procedure is generally recommended to further enhance the extraction efficiency (Akhmadiyeva et al., 2025; Bartoňová et al., 2025; Urakaev et al., 2020).

4. Joint extraction of Li and other elements

As reviewed in Section 2, Li concentrations in mining and mineral-processing wastes are generally too low to be economically viable to extract Li as the only element. For design of a full (or at least multi-component) utilization of given material, knowledge of other elements extractability is crucial – the most interesting literature findings in this area are discussed below.

4.1. Joint extraction of Li and Rb (or Cs)

Since Rb and Cs belong to alkaline metals as well, their modes of occurrence and/or leaching behaviour are in many aspects similar to Li. Literature results of co-extraction of Li and Rb (or other elements) are summarized in Table 2.

In case of zinnwaldite-originating wastes and traditional procedures – good extraction rates were achieved not only for Li (77–91 %) but also for Rb where extraction percentages were even higher (90–93 %) (Jandová et al., 2010; Kristianová et al., 2023; Shuiping et al., 2024; Vu et al., 2013). Even higher recovery of both elements (98.7 % Li and 97.27 % Rb) was achieved by roasting lithium porcelain stone with

Na_2SO_4 and CaCl_2 at 850 °C followed by water leaching (Wang et al., 2020). Alternative approach based on bioleaching was tested as well – using either silicate bacteria *LM-1* (H. Li et al., 2022) or *Aspergillus niger* (Ertan, 2023); extraction efficiency is then somewhat lower (71.68 or 78.67 % Li and 80.42 or 37.44 % Rb) and the time needed for such procedure is generally higher – e.g. 31 days (Ertan, 2023); nevertheless, there is no need to heat the material to high temperatures (energy savings) or to use dangerous chemicals.

4.2. Joint extraction of Li and Al (or other elements)

Joint extraction of Li and Al is typical for Al-containing wastes, such as bauxite-processing wastes (Han et al., 2021; Tang et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2021) or coal gangue/ash (Li et al., 2017; Qin et al., 2022; Shao et al., 2022; Zhang and Honaker, 2020), as shown in Table 3.

Using sulfuric acid/sulfate salts (Dong et al., 2024a; Qin et al., 2022; Tang et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2021), NaOH (Kuang et al., 2015; C. Li et al., 2024) or even calcination without additives (H. Chen et al., 2022; Shao et al., 2022; Zhang and Honaker, 2020) are the most commonly used approaches providing good Li extraction efficiency. Aluminium extraction rate is generally somewhat lower 30–89 % (C. Li et al., 2024; Qin et al., 2022; Tang et al., 2023; Zhang and Honaker, 2020; Zhang et al., 2021); however, roasting the coal gangue without additives followed by nitric acid leaching provided 95.2 % Al recovery, which was even higher than that of Li (80.5 %) (Shao et al., 2022). Very high Al

Fig. 8B. Procedures of Li extraction from fly ash (^a Fang et al., 2023; ^b Gao et al., 2024; ^c C. Li et al., 2024; ^d Li et al., 2017; ^e Qin et al., 2015; ^f Rezaei et al., 2023; ^g Rezaei et al., 2022; ^h Xing et al., 2024; ⁱ Xu et al., 2021). Conversion note: 1 ppm = 10–4 %.

extraction rate (nearly 100 %) was achieved by NaOH digestion at 136 °C from Li-extraction gypsum residue originating from lepidolite processing where Li extraction rate was 96.4 % (Kuang et al., 2015).

To avoid heating the sample to high temperatures, extraction of Li from coal gangue by intercalation was studied as well – the tested coal gangue was intercalated by DMSO at 60 °C followed by 3M HCl leaching at 90 °C; extraction rates were somewhat lower (17.55 % Li and 10.55 % Al), but the main advantage of this approach is energy saving and reducing emissions during calcination (H. Chen et al., 2022). If higher extraction rates are preferred, traditional approach (calcination followed by acid leaching) applied on the same material led to 94.44 % Li and 65.69 % Al recovery (H. Chen et al., 2022).

4.3. Joint extraction of Li and Ga, Ge or REE (and other elements)

The waste materials frequently studied in terms of Li-Ga-Ge joint extraction are coal gangues and coal slags or fly ashes; if emphasis is based on joint extraction of Li and REE (or F), then rare earth electrolytic molten salt slag is a promising waste material – the most interesting results in this research field are summarized in Table 4.

If coal gangue, slag or fly ash samples were studied as a source of Li and Ga or Ge, Na₂CO₃ roasting at 800–875 °C followed by acid leaching is one of the most common procedure (Gao et al., 2024; C. Li et al., 2024; Rezaei et al., 2023, 2022) providing >90 % Li and Ga and moderately lower extraction of Ge. Low roasting temperatures 300–400 °C (energy saving) were tested with KOH, NaOH or H₂O₂ additives - if followed by water leaching at 30 °C, 28–41 % Li and 36–52 % Ga were extracted (Pan et al., 2024). Calcination without additive at 600–750 °C (followed by 1.2M HCl leaching) led to good extraction rates of Li, REE, P, Sr or Mg

(Zhang and Honaker, 2020). Rare earth molten salt electrolytic slag originates from electrolytic precipitation of rare earth metals from the melt of their salts, and it can be used as a promising source of numerous valuable elements. The results listed in Table 4 suggest that regardless of the procedure used, good extraction rates can be achieved for Li (>96 %) and REE (>90 %) (X. Li et al., 2024; Tong et al., 2023; Yang et al., 2024).

Useful information and suggestions for further research can be inferred from sequential extraction studies applied on such waste materials. Tessier's sequential extraction procedure applied on 3 red mud samples (Gu et al., 2018) revealed similar distribution of Li, Sc, Y and La-Lu – dominant dissolution in NH₂OH.HCl in 25 % CH₃COOH, which is generally attributed to Fe-Mn oxides association. Minor percentages of these elements were dissolved in CH₃COONa/CH₃COOH at pH = 5 (which is used for dissolution of carbonates) or in HNO₃/H₂O₂ at pH = 2 (85 °C), which is generally used for organic matter association. In contrast, Ga was prevalently dissolved by water or by HNO₃/H₂O₂, which corresponds with dominant water-leachable fraction and minor organic matter bound species. Nb was predominantly dissolved by HNO₃/H₂O₂ (Gu et al., 2018).

Information on distribution of valuable elements among individual fractions during minerals/ores processing and separation is important as well (and can be used for designing the optimal procedure for the extraction of these elements or for selecting optimal waste as a feed-stock). For example, in case of alumina production from bauxite (Bayer process), after separation of red mud and Na aluminate solution, Sc and Ti were enriched in red mud (54–120 ppm and 0.98–5.34 %) while Ga and Li enter sodium aluminate liquor (60–120 ppm Ga and 1.5–4.9 % Li) (Y. Chen et al., 2022). During the utilization of feldspar processing waste, mica containing light fraction can be used as a source of Li

Fig. 9. Procedures of Li extraction from zinnwaldite and other mining wastes (conc. = concentrate) (^a Hu and Wang, 2021; ^b Huang et al., 2020; ^c Jandová et al., 2010; ^d Jandová et al., 2009; ^e Kristianová et al., 2023; ^f Li et al., 2022; ^g X. Li et al., 2024; ^h Martin et al., 2017; ⁱ Shuiping et al., 2024; ^j Tong et al., 2023; ^k Vu et al., 2013).

whereas Nb or Ta can be extracted from heavy fraction, (Vrbický and Příkryl, 2021).

In any case, the aforementioned waste materials contain also certain amount of toxic and hazardous elements that could be leached out as well— such as Cr (Bartoňová and Raclavská, 2022; Zhang and Honaker, 2020), Cd (Bartoňová et al., 2020; C. Li et al., 2024), Tl and Be (C. Li et al., 2024) or V (Bartoňová et al., 2023; Rezaei et al., 2022, 2023). For example, high leaching efficiency of U after (NH₄)₂SO₄ roasting at 400 °C was observed by Yang et al. (2019); Yang et al. (2019) in case of coal ash where UO₂SO₄ was formed, which is important conclusion namely in terms of the choice of the extraction procedure for U-rich coal ashes. Unfortunately, research in this area is quite limited (most studies are focused primarily on valuable elements).

And, during extraction of Li from Li-rich red mud (by neutralization

by 0.01M HCl and 25 % acetic acid leaching) not only 58–60 % Li but also >95 % Na and 85 % Ca was dissolved as well (Gu et al., 2020b). Similarly, during Li extraction from bauxite flotation tailings not only 92 % Li but also 57 % K was leached (D. Han et al., 2024). Despite Na, K and Ca are not toxic and hazardous elements, their high dissolution rates are disadvantageous because it might lead to increased demands paid on Li separation from the leachate. Even if leaching of Na, K (or Ca) was not generally studied in other papers, similar behaviour can be expected also in other case studies.

4.4. Examples of optimization of the extraction procedures regarding target elements and the most common extraction patterns

If more elements are to be recovered from a given waste material, the

Table 1
Comparison of the most common extraction procedures.

Extraction method	Advantages	Drawbacks	References
Acid method (mostly H ₂ SO ₄)	Highly adaptable to various waste materials, high efficiency, easy to control, quick extraction	Corrosion of equipment, high consumption of H ₂ SO ₄ , potential SO ₂ emissions, requires neutralization, high impurity levels in leachate, large waste residue discharge, low selectivity	(Cao et al., 2024; Sarker et al., 2022; Tian-ming et al.; M. Yang et al., 2025)
Alkaline method	High extraction rate, generally less corrosive and less environmental impact	Energy intensive calcination, high requirements for equipment	(Cao et al., 2024; Yang et al., 2025)
Salt (mostly carbonate or sulfate) roasting method	Lower cost (with Na salts), simple process, less corrosion of equipment, lower levels of impurities in leachate	High energy consumption, higher cost if K ₂ SO ₄ is used	(Tian-ming et al.; Yang et al., 2025)
Bioleaching	Avoiding aggressive chemicals, eco-friendly, good efficiency, lower temperatures (energy saving)	Longer extraction duration, limited to certain matrixes, can be inhibited by impurities	(Ertan, 2023; H. Li et al., 2022)

choice of the optimal procedure may require detailed evaluation.

For example, in case of coal FA, optimal extraction conditions should be selected according to target elements: if only Li and Ga are to be extracted, then HCl leaching at 30–50 °C is good (with ca. 82–90 % extraction efficiency for both elements); however, if REE are to be extracted as well, using 30–50 °C provides only 30–65 % REE recovery and HCl leaching at 70–80 °C is to be preferred (improving REE extraction to 90 % while extraction of Li and Ga remains unchanged). And the concentration of HCl should be optimized as well - if REE are to be extracted along with Li and Ga, then 2M HCl (sufficient for efficient extraction of Li and Ga) should be elevated to 3–4M HCl to obtain 90 % recovery of REE – otherwise REE extraction efficiency is somewhat worse (Gao et al., 2024).

Detailed extraction study of coal gangue (Qin et al., 2022) provides results for 11 elements (Li, Al, Mg, Fe, Sr, Cu, Zn, Mn, Ga, V and Ti) and 2 alternative extraction procedures – i) roasting with (NH₄)₂SO₄+NH₄Cl at 400 °C followed by water leaching and ii) roasting with (NH₄)₂SO₄ at 400 °C followed by water leaching. As the selection of the optimal procedure should be done not only for Li but with the view of other elements, it is worth further discussion – Fig. 10 was plotted based on these data (Qin et al., 2022) and summarizes extraction rates of these 11 elements by these 2 procedures. There is no doubt that higher Li and Al extraction rates were achieved by (NH₄)₂SO₄+NH₄Cl roasting. Nevertheless, complete comparison of these 2 procedures shown in Fig. 10 suggests that (NH₄)₂SO₄ roasting without NH₄Cl is advantageous namely for Ti, V, Ga, Mn, and Zn thereby decreasing Li and Al extraction from 80.83 to 65 % (Li) and from 56.35 to 24.16 % (Al). As roasting temperature was the same in both procedures, moderate advantage of this procedure is avoiding addition of NH₄Cl. So overall evaluation should be related to the individual selection of target elements, economic calculations etc. And it should be mentioned in this context that the coal gangue sample was not dissolved totally - the solid residue provided specific surface area of 222 m²/g which is a promising value for the preparation of adsorbents (Qin et al., 2022).

In summary, the aforementioned results indicate that numerous elements that can be efficiently co-extracted with Li belong to strategic or critical energy transition minerals (Vivoda et al., 2025b), such as – Al,

Table 2
Joint extraction of Li and Rb (or other elements) from waste materials.

Material	Procedure	% extracted	References
Zinnwaldite waste – concentrate 1.21 % Li and 0.84 % Rb	Roasting with CaCO ₃ , 825 °C, water leaching 95 °C, carbonation	90 % Li 90 % Rb	Jandová et al. (2010)
Zinnwaldite waste 1.29 % Li and 0.94 % Rb	Sintering with CaCO ₃ , 825 °C, water leaching 95 °C	84 % Li 91 % Rb	Vu et al. (2013)
Zinnwaldite tailings	Silicate bacteria <i>LM-1</i> bioleaching (microbial pretreatment for enhanced flotation)	71.68 % Li 80.42 % Rb	H. Li et al. (2022)
Zinnwaldite	CaO and B ₂ O ₃ thermal activation additives H ₂ SO ₄ leaching	91.32 % Li 93.09 % Rb 81.14 % Fe 95.00 % Al 71.12 % K	Shuiping et al. (2024)
Zinnwaldite	CaCl ₂ roasting 1000 °C, water leaching 90 °C	77 % Li 90 % Rb 90 % K	Kristianová et al. (2023)
Clay containing B waste	<i>Aspergillus niger</i> bioleaching, 31 days	78.67 % Li 37.44 % Rb 30.47 % Cs	Ertan (2023)
Lithium porcelain stone	Na ₂ SO ₄ + CaCl ₂ roasting 850 °C, 60 min. Water leaching, lab temp., 60 min	98.7 % Li 97.27 % Rb 49.8 % Na 37.9 % K 98.40 % Cs	Wang et al. (2020)

Ga, Ge, REE, V, Ta etc. Even though concentrations and modes of occurrence of these valuable elements are variable in individual waste sources, certain common features (co-extraction patterns) can be identified there, which is summarized in Table 5.

Clay minerals usually contain higher levels of other alkaline metals, such as Rb or Cs, and current research documents that these elements can be efficiently co-extracted from such materials (Ertan, 2023; Jandová et al., 2010; Wang et al., 2020). Bauxite processing residues (like red mud or overhaul slag) and coal gangue or ash contain high levels of Al which leads to intensive research of its co-extraction with Li (Fang et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2021); in case of coal gangue and ash often also with Ga and Ge (Rezaei et al., 2022; Sun et al., 2024) while in case of bauxite residues along with Sc (Baştürkçü, 2021). It is not surprising that REE electrolytic molten salt slag contained high levels of REE which led to their successful co-extraction experiments with Li (X. Li et al., 2024; Yang et al., 2024).

4.5. Pilot-scale results

Pilot-scale or semi-industrial studies related to this topic are extremely scarce in literature; nevertheless, currently available results document feasibility of the extraction of Li (and other elements) even in a larger scale. Semi-industrial sorting pre-enrichment experiments with coal gangue were reported by Dai et al. (2023). Using vibrating feeder and X-ray sensor, around 31 % of the waste rock were excluded thereby reducing the cost for subsequent refining process (and providing the concentrate with 194.12 ppm Li and 27.73 ppm Ga). Pilot-scale

Table 3
Joint extraction of Li and Al (and other elements) from waste materials.

Material	Procedure	% extracted	Ref.
Dried Al-cryolite electrolyte (from bauxite) 12.2 % Al+1.96 % Li	H ₂ SO ₄ roasting in N ₂ , 325 °C, water leaching 80 °C	87.55 % Li 30.30 % Al	Tang et al. (2023)
Bauxite mine tailings	H ₂ SO ₄ +H ₃ PO ₄ leaching (100 °C), no roasting	88.64 % Al 96.36 % Li	Zhang et al. (2021)
Bauxite	CaO digestion, 260 °C KOH leaching	85.6 % Li 80.09 % Al	Han et al. (2021)
Overhaul slag (Al industry)	H ₂ SO ₄ roasting, 360 °C, water leaching	99.5 % Li 72.57 % Al	Dong et al. (2024a)
Gypsum residue from Li extraction from lepidolite	NaOH digestion 136 °C, 60 min	96.4 % Li 100 % Al	Kuang et al. (2015)
Coal FA	NaOH desilication + HCl leaching	82.23 % Li	Li et al. (2017)
0.2 % Li ₂ O		76.72 % Al	
42.17 % Al ₂ O ₃			
Coal FA	Na ₂ S ₂ O ₇ milling	95.45 % Li	Fang et al. (2023)
	Na ₂ S ₂ O ₇ pressure leaching 230 °C	95.58 % Al	
Coal gangue	(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ :NH ₄ Cl roasting 1 h, 400 °C, water leaching	80.83 % Li 56.35 % Al 32.77 % Fe*	Qin et al. (2022)
Coal gangue	Calcination 600 °C, 2 h + 3M HCl leaching 90 °C	94.44 % Li 65.69 % Al 0.38 % Nb 70.26 % Fe	H. Chen et al. (2022)
Coal gangue	Intercalation by DMSO 60 °C, 24 h + 3M HCl leaching 90 °C	17.55 % Li 10.55 % Al 0.41 % Nb 22.31 % F	H. Chen et al. (2022)
Coal gangue	Roasting 400–800 °C 0.5–3 h; HNO ₃ leaching 2 h, 150 °C	80.5 % Li 95.2 % Al 56.4 % Ga 2.1 % Fe	Shao et al. (2022)
Coal refuse sample	Calcination 600–750 °C 1.2M HCl leaching, 75 °C	70 %**Li 45 %**Al 90 %**LREE 45 %**HREE 95 %**P 40 %**K 70 %**Mg 30 %**Cr 90 %**Sr 30 %**V	Zhang and Honaker (2020)

Explanations: *Detailed information in Fig. 10; ** Rough estimation (data from graph).

Table 4
Joint extraction of Li and Ga, Ge or REE (and other elements) from waste materials.

Material	Procedure	% extracted	References
Coal gangue	High-gradient magnetic separation and step-by-step chemical extraction method	88.00 % Li 80.07 % Ga	Sun et al. (2024)
Coal gasification slag	Water leaching (30 °C, 2 h) after: NaOH roasting (300 °C) KOH roasting (300 °C) Na ₂ O ₂ roasting (300 °C) Na ₂ CO ₃ roasting (1000 °C) K ₂ CO ₃ roasting (1000 °C)	40.81 % Li and 47.89 % Ga 41.19 % Li and 35.60 % Ga 28.04 %** Li and 52.40 % Ga 28.21 % Li and 48.58 % Ga 34.29 % Li and 38.61 % Ga	Pan et al. (2024)
Coal fly ash	Na ₂ CO ₃ roasting (850 °C) 0.5M citric acid leaching (30 °C)	99.35 % Li 89.58 % Ge 81.23 % V	Rezaei et al. (2022)
CFB fly ash	Na ₂ CO ₃ roasting 800 °C, 2 h, 3M HCl leaching	90.4 % Li 90.5 % Ga 92.7 % REE	Gao et al. (2024)
Coal fly ash	Na ₂ CO ₃ roasting Bioleaching (<i>Pseudomonas putida</i>), 75 °C	98 % Li 83 % Ge 97 % V	Rezaei et al. (2023)
Coal fly ash	Na ₂ CO ₃ fusion 875 °C 0.4M citric acid leaching 50 °C	Extracted: >90 % Li, Ga, Be 70–90 % Ge, Se, Sr, Zr, Nb, Cd, Cs, Hf 10–30 % Ta, Tl	C. Li et al. (2024)
Coal refuse sample	Calcination 600–750 °C 1.2M HCl leaching, 75 °C	70 %* Li 90 %* LREE 45 %* HREE 45 %* Al 95 %* P 40 %* K 70 %* Mg 30 %* Cr 90 %* Sr 30 %* V	Zhang and Honaker (2020)
Rare earth molten salt electrolytic slag	CaO (H ₂ O), 60 °C, 120 min 4M H ₂ SO ₄ leaching, 70 °C, 60 min Oxalic acid and trisodium phosphate precipitation	99.41 % Li 95.72 % REE	X. Li et al. (2024)
Rare earth electrolytic molten salt slag	80 % NaOH leaching, 200 °C, 3 h	Li 99.22 % REE 99.05 % F 98.23 %	Yang et al. (2024)
Rare earth electrolytic molten salt slag	CaO + Al ₂ (SO ₄) ₃ roasting, 2 h 3M H ₂ SO ₄ leaching, 100 °C, 4 h	Li 96.69 % Nd 92.47 % Pr 91.56 % Gd 91.08 % F 96.8 %	Tong et al. (2023)
Bauxite flotation tailings	NaHCO ₃ digestion 280 °C, water washing	91.75 % Li 57.46 % K	D. Han et al. (2024)
Red mud	2-step H ₂ SO ₄ leaching, 90 °C, 2 h	86.5 % Li 82.4 % Sc	Baştürkcü (2021)
Red mud	Neutralization by 0.01M HCl, leaching by 25 % CH ₃ COOH, 95 %, 60 min	58–60 % Li >95 % Na 85 % Ca	Gu et al. (2020a)

Explanations: * Rough estimation (data from graph), **400 °C.

Fig. 10. Elemental leaching rates achieved by water leaching after (NH₄)₂SO₄ or (NH₄)₂SO₄+NH₄Cl roasting – based on the data from Qin et al. (2015); Qin et al. (2015).

Table 5
The most common co-extraction patterns.

Waste source	Common co-extraction patterns	References
Wastes originating from zinnwaldite and clays processing	Li + Rb and Cs	(Ertan, 2023; Jandová et al., 2010; Wang et al., 2020)
Coal gangue and ash	Li + Al, Ga, or Ge	(Fang et al., 2023; C. Li et al., 2024; Shao et al., 2022)
Red mud and bauxite-processing residues	Li + Al, Sc, Na, or Ca	(Baştürkücü, 2021; Gu et al., 2020a; Zhang et al., 2021)
REE electrolytic molten salt slag	Li + REE	(X. Li et al., 2024; Yang et al., 2024)

technology was also developed to produce 99.9 % Li₂CO₃, K₂SO₄, Al₂(SO₄)₃ and Rb- and Cs-formates by H₂SO₄-fluoride leaching of fluorite extraction tailings (Suss et al., 2022). Pilot-scale H₂SO₄ extraction of Li, Al and Ga from FBC FA was conducted by J. Li et al. (2022) leading to extraction efficiency of Al, Li and Ga being 95.2 %, 94.2 % and 87.7 %, respectively. It is worth mentioning that the experiment was proposed as self-heating because the heat needed for 140 °C extraction originated only from dilution of H₂SO₄ in water (which is a practical economic approach).

Nevertheless, scaling of Li extraction technologies from mining and mineral processing wastes is also connected with policy and investment incentives encouraging their integration into existing mining operations (Zhang et al., 2025), which is helpful for mitigating the environmental impacts associated with traditional mining practices and promoting the sustainable management of waste materials (Sedda et al., 2023; Simões et al., 2024). Furthermore, effective waste classification systems are critical to maximize the economic potential of these resources. Proper classification can distinguish between hazardous and non-hazardous waste, enabling focused investment in remediation and recovery practices (Siekierka et al., 2022). Incentives and financial mechanisms encouraging the valorisation of mining wastes could support companies that invest in technology for extraction of Li and other critical minerals (Lèbre and Corder, 2015). By fostering a circular economy approach in the mining sector, this would not only enhance resource recovery but also align with broader sustainability goals (Araya et al., 2021; Sharma et al., 2023). Ultimately, integrating these elements into a cohesive strategy could significantly shift the dynamics of Li supply chains,

making them more resilient and environmentally friendly.

5. Discussion

5.1. Discussion of extraction procedure selection

Previous sections document that efficient methods for Li extraction from mining and mineral processing wastes exist. However, to address the increasing demands for minimizing and utilization of huge amounts of industrial wastes, optimal procedure should be selected with the view of broader context.

Crucial aspects affecting the choice of the optimal procedure are depicted in Fig. 11. They are waste characteristics, parameters of the extraction procedure, environmental impact of such procedure (in relation to the given waste), economic viability and geopolitical considerations. None of these parameters should be assessed in isolation but as a part of an overall assessment, for example:

- i) Material with relatively high Li content may not be the best option if the concentration of other rare components is low and/or the levels of toxic or radioactive elements are high. Elemental modes of occurrence and concentrations of interfering elements are important as well. It is also worth mentioning that (in some instances) valuable elements can exhibit higher levels in gangue interbeds (rock partings) than in the raw material seams themselves.
- ii) Method with moderately higher extraction rates may not be the best choice at all if (e.g.) hazardous or expensive chemicals and/or energy intensive long-term roasting are required (that is often accompanied by adding huge amounts of fusion/sintering additives often producing emissions or increased levels of dissolved salts). And, the separation of individual components from the leachate can be even more problematic than the conversion of the ions into the solution. Time factor should also be taken into consideration as methods being more environmentally friendly may require longer time (e.g., bioleaching).
- iii) Another important aspect relates to the production of new waste - i.e., optimal procedure enables the utilization of all components of a waste (thereby producing minimal amount of a new waste). It is also practical if some unusable components can be removed prior to roasting, leaching or similar practices thereby reducing amount of energy, emissions, and wastewater or simplifying the consequent separation.
- iv) Local availability of the waste (including water for leaching or other components) is also important as it can differ a lot in individual regions and relates to transportation costs.

Novel and promising methods have been described in literature for Li extraction from traditional Li ores, such as electrochemical methods (Zhang et al., 2024) or membrane assisted crystallization approach (Villa Gomez et al., 2024) – these new methods could be tested also for mining and minerals processing wastes. And, with the aim of economic and environmental sustainability, methods using lower amount of water, roasting additives or other harsh chemicals and lower roasting/leaching temperatures could be proposed, evaluated, and preferred to traditional procedures. Testing of the most promising laboratory methods in pilot-scale or semi-industrial conditions could be a next beneficial step.

5.2. Discussion of economic aspect

An important part of complex evaluation of a given secondary source and optimal extraction procedure is economic consideration. Despite high extraction efficiency of Li, recovery of Li as the only element is not expected to be financially viable; therefore, incorporating Li extraction into more complex extraction schemes is a more feasible approach.

Fig. 11. Selection of the optimal procedure for Li extraction from individual mining and mineral-processing wastes.

Current research (reviewed in this paper) documents that co-extraction of Li + Ga and Ge, Li + Al, Li + REE etc. is technologically possible. Nevertheless, studies evaluating cut-off grade values or economic feasibility in this area are extremely scarce or nearly non-existent.

Even if numerous promising results have been published in literature, more research is still needed for the secondary sources to meaningfully supplement Li supply chains (therefore it is not very likely in the short-term horizon). Despite this, there is an urgent need to continue the current research and testing because focusing only to short-term sustainability (and short-term cost savings) could lead to hazardous long-term environmental and geopolitical consequences in the future (Vivoda et al., 2025a). Moreover, ensuring Li sustainability in future is thought to be even more challenging than now as the differences between the supply and demand will increase significantly (International Energy Agency, 2024) as well as the urge to handle the increasing amount of mining and mineral processing wastes.

5.3. Discussion of broader critical minerals strategy

Despite its great significance, the economic perspective constitutes only one pillar of the so called “critical minerals trilemma” framework including also national security and socio-environmental sustainability. For example, despite Li demand is strongly related with the urge of energy transition and introducing “greener technologies” (Attfilio, 2025), if environmental aspect is neglected during its production, intensive mineral extraction may paradoxically lead to environmental degradation (Vivoda et al., 2024a). And, as Li (and other critical elements) play an important role in geoeconomic and strategic planning due to their increasing indispensability in renewable energy, defence (advanced military) or space technologies, their extraction from secondary sources helps to reduce geopolitical supply risk (Vivoda et al., 2024b). Therefore, the economic aspect of Li extraction from mining and mineral processing wastes should be balanced with security and socio-environmental sustainability objectives because otherwise it could inevitably lead to long-term environmental and geopolitical risks (Sun et al., 2025; Vivoda and Loginova, 2025).

5.4. Latest research – emerging trends in 2023–2025 literature

Latest research in this field predominantly deals with secondary sources rich in Li (and other valuable elements), such as overhaul slag (Dong et al., 2024a, 2024c), spent Al electrolyte (Wang et al., 2025; Zhou et al., 2025), electrolytic aluminium slag (Qin et al., 2025) or REMSES (Z. Yang et al., 2025); papers on Li recovery from coal gangue are also abundant (Wei et al., 2025; Xie et al., 2025a) as it is produced in vast quantities throughout the world. Papers focusing on new types of

wastes in this context are emerging as well – studying (e.g.) waste REE polishing powder (Chen et al., 2025) or Ti white waste (Lei et al., 2024).

There are studies highlighting the significance of proper pre-enrichment for efficient Li separation (Sun et al., 2024), research papers aimed to implementation of these technologies into current mining practices (Zhang et al., 2025) and development of greener extraction procedures (such as bioleaching) (Iqbal et al., 2023) or recyclable leaching system (Xie et al., 2025b).

High demands placed on the separation of Li and other elements lead to intensive development in this area - with attention paid to separation of Li and Al (Dong et al., 2025), Li and Co/Ni (Han et al., 2025) Li and Ga (Fang et al., 2024), or Li and Mg (Estay and Troncoso, 2025); efficient separation of Li can be achieved (e.g.) by adsorption using newly synthesized Li ion sieves (Long et al., 2024). Another promising approach involves using Li-leaching agents that can also bind interfering ions (e.g., Ca or Mg) present in the solution (Aladağ and Erdem, 2025). To facilitate separation of individual valuable elements, particular attention is paid also to selective recovery procedures, such as two-stage roasting (Xie et al., 2025a) or two-stage leaching (Wei et al., 2025).

It is not surprising that to ensure sufficient Li supply in the future, there is intensive research in the traditional field of Li extraction from brines (Guo et al., 2025; Kong et al., 2025) or black mass (Mannu et al., 2025), which is somewhat beyond the topic of this review. Nevertheless, some of these methods can be used even when Li is extracted from mining and mineral processing residues (Asif et al., 2025; Yoo et al., 2024).

Despite being extremely scarce, papers evaluating economic and environmental aspects exist (Tang et al., 2025). Papers evaluating technological readiness level of Li extraction are almost non-existent; and if they exist, they are focused on Li extraction from discarded batteries (Ilyas et al., 2025; Protopapa et al., 2025; Yazıcı et al., 2025) or on direct Li extraction from brines (Boroumand and Razmjou, 2024); unfortunately, they do not address mining and mineral processing wastes. From economic and environmental point of view, every effort made to introduce the extraction of Li (and other critical elements) into current mining and mineral processing practices is highly beneficial (Botelho Junior, 2025).

6. Conclusions

Although Li mining expansion continues, this source is projected to increasingly lag behind the rapidly growing Li demand (International Energy Agency, 2024). An alternative approach lies (i.a.) in the recovery of Li from mining and mineral processing wastes. In addition to providing Li (and other critical elements) and practical utilization of the vast amount of mining and mineral processing wastes, there is also a

benefit of supporting national strategic and defence objectives as well as notable environmental and social advantages. Li extraction from mining and minerals processing wastes can support critical minerals strategies particularly in the following areas (which are often interconnected):

- i) Strengthening supply security (it reduces dependence on primary mining concentrated in a few countries thereby diversifying supply and mitigating geopolitical and market risks)
- ii) Improving resource efficiency (aligning with circular economy principles)
- iii) Reducing environmental and social impact (avoiding social and permitting challenges associated with opening new mines; reduced mining minimizes ecological degradation)
- iv) Supporting domestic value chains (building local industrial capacity supporting domestic supply chains)
- v) Enhancing strategic autonomy and innovation (investment in waste recovery technologies encourages innovation and strategic autonomy)

Despite significant **technological progress** in this field, significant gaps and challenges remain to be addressed, particularly in the following areas:

- i) *Implementation of pre-concentration technologies* – Removal of Li-poor material prior to extraction itself allows using lower amounts of hazardous chemicals, water, and energy (e.g., for heating).
- ii) *Behaviour of toxic and hazardous elements* – Since these materials contain also harmful components, research should focus not only on valuable elements but also on the redistribution and transformation pathways of hazardous ones during the overall extraction process.
- iii) *Co-extraction and separation challenges* – Intensive research should be focused on novel and efficient separation technologies. As the co-extraction of Li and other valuable elements brings numerous additional (including hazardous) components into solution, effective downstream separation becomes crucial—not only to recover valuable materials but also to manage toxic elements responsibly.
- iv) *Circular economy integration* – In line with circular economy principles, comprehensive studies should aim at the full utilization of waste materials. This includes developing processes suitable for the co-extraction of lithium and other critical minerals (Ga, Ge, REE, V, etc.), as well as strategies to reuse extraction residues and manage new waste streams.

In addition to technological development, other research and policy priorities related to the **broader technical, economic, and strategic context** are as follows:

- i) *Economic feasibility* – There is an urgent need of overall techno-economic evaluation, including estimate of Li cut-off grades in various mining and mineral processing wastes (considering their composition and origin, and in relation to other critical minerals availability). Evaluating these processes within the framework of circular economy is extremely important as well as the integration of such technologies into existing mining and mineral processing operations. Financial mechanisms encouraging the valorisation of mining wastes could support companies that invest in technologies for recovery of Li and other critical minerals (including pilot-scale investment).
- ii) *Environmental impact* – Overall environmental impact assessment of these procedures is needed as well - including both positive and negative effects of these technologies, such as reducing opening new mines, minimizing landfilling and stockpiling of original waste, possible generation of new waste streams (wastewater,

emissions, solid residues) or (in a broader perspective) how lithium-based technologies contribute to replacing fossil fuel-based energy systems. To maximize the recovery potential of these resources, the effective classification systems are crucial (distinguishing e.g. between hazardous and non-hazardous wastes). A key factor is also environmental regulation alignment of newly emerged and economically promising technologies with current and future environmental standards.

- iii) *Social and geopolitical aspects* – Evaluating the societal and geopolitical implications of implementing these technologies would be beneficial as well, particularly how secondary lithium recovery from mining and processing wastes could reduce dependence on conventional supply chains and mitigate geopolitical risks.

Progress in these technological and socio-economic domains will pave the way for pilot-scale and semi-industrial testing, which is a necessary step toward large-scale deployment.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Lucie Bartoňová: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Conceptualization. **Helena Raclavská:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Barbora Svědová:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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